

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE, BIOLOGICAL AND ANTHROPOGENIC FACTORS ON PLANT GENETIC RESOURCES IN CENTRAL ASIA AND IMPORTANCE OF BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION IN THE CASE OF WILD APPLE (*MALUS SIEVERSII*) AND BREAD WHEAT

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According to the data of international scientific centers and statistical studies, the Central Asian region is experiencing climate change twice as fast as the world average. This means that in the future, the negative effects of high temperature in the region will increase dramatically, high mountain glaciers, which are water sources for the region, will decrease, and ultimately, negative factors such as lack of water for farming will cause great damage to agriculture and natural vegetation cover, as well as biodiversity.

In addition, new disease and pest species are emerging that have adapted to the negative factors of climate change before other organisms and pose a great threat to both agriculture industry and natural biodiversity. Deeper penetration of the human factor into natural spaces, the development and expansion of agriculture and tourism lead to changes in natural environments, especially to decrease in the level of plant diversity.

In reducing the negative impact of climate change on agriculture and food security, as well as the negative impact of new dangerous biological factors, the wild ancestors of cultivated crops and their biodiversity are of great practical importance due to the presence of resistance/tolerance genes, that is sources for resistance. Scientific evidence suggests that wild ancestors are generally richer in resistance genes than domesticated ones. Because of this, the conservation of wild ancestors of agricultural crops and their use in increasing the resistance of cultivated crops are among the most urgent issues of today.

As a result of the scientific research on the use of old and local varieties of bread wheat in breeding projects at the Institute of Genetics and PEB of AS Uz, a new variety was created from an ancient accession that is on the verge of extinction, and a variety that shows high positive indicators in drought conditions and is expanding its area in practice. In addition, research work is being carried out on the collection and conservation of *Malus sieversii* species, wild ancestor of the apple, which is the favorite fruit crop of the population of Central Asia, and which is currently in danger of decreasing biodiversity, as well as using it in breeding projects. As a result of the conducted research, samples of old accession of bread wheat and wild apple were collected from different regions of the Republic, characterized by molecular genetic description and created their gene pool.